

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

D 3.5 Business support intermediate services portfolio

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, 3.5 of INTEGER, provides a comprehensive follow-up to the first stage of Task 3.3, specifically regarding the mentoring process. In this document, readers will find a detailed account of the activities and outcomes related to the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital projects through regional Col-laborathons.

The document is structured as follows:

- 1) **Regional Process Development:** An explanation of the mentoring process developed in each region involved in the project. This section highlights the unique approaches and methodologies employed to support social-digital projects in different local contexts.
- 2) **Collective Activities:** A detailed overview of the activities that were carried out collaboratively across regions. This includes organizing meetings between social-driven innovators and business leaders, facilitating idea exchanges, and fostering potential partnerships.
- 3) **Synergies and Conclusions:** An analysis of the synergies identified between different regional models and the conclusions drawn from these interactions. This section also discusses the strategies developed to promote convergence between business-driven and social-driven approaches to innovation.

The Col-laborathons served as pivotal events for identifying innovative solutions tailored to regional needs. Key stakeholders were instrumental in evaluating proposals and selecting the most promising projects, thereby ensuring alignment with local realities.

Significant milestones were achieved in stakeholder engagement, establishing a robust foundation for ongoing collaboration and knowledge exchange. By presenting these detailed accounts, activities, and analyses, this document aims to offer valuable insights and practical strategies for advancing social-digital projects within the INTEGER framework.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
LIST OF FIGURES.....	6
SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS	7
1.INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 BACKGROUND AND AIM	8
1.2 STRUCTURE OF THE DELIVERABLE	8
1.3 METHODS	8
1.4 SYNERGIES WITH OTHER TASKS AND DELIVERABLES.....	9
2.MENTORING PROCESS IN EACH REGION	11
2.1 KRAKOW MODEL	11
2.1.1 <i>Training topic</i>	11
2.1.2 <i>Implementation phase</i>	12
2.1.3 <i>Social innovators involved</i>	12
2.1.4 <i>Mentoring based on experiences and conclusions from AHathon edition I</i>	13
2.1.5 <i>Social impact achieved</i>	15
2.2 HAMBURG MODEL.....	16
2.2.1 <i>Social innovators in Hamburg</i>	18
2.2.2 <i>Social impact achieved</i>	19
2.3 CATALONIA MODEL	19
2.3.1 <i>Social innovators involved</i>	19
2.3.2 <i>Methodologies used</i>	20
3.TRAINING ACTIVITIES JOINING THE THREE MODELS	22
3.1 THE COL·LABER TRAINING DAY	22
3.2 TRAINING SESSION 1: “HOW TO SELL WITH AI AND LINKEDIN”	24
3.3 TRAINING SESSION 2: “COMMUNICATE, IMPACT AND TRANSFORM: THE IM-PERFECT PITCH”	25
4.SYNERGIES BETWEEN MODELS	26
4.1 KRAKOW MODEL	26
4.1 HAMBURG MODEL.....	27
4.2 CATALONIA MODEL.....	27
4.3 SYNERGIES BETWEEN REGIONS.....	27
5.CONCLUSIONS.....	29

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE 1. KRAKOW AHATHON	11
FIGURE 2. KRAKOW AHATHON	15
FIGURE 3. AGENDA OF COL·LABER TRAINING DAY	23
FIGURE 4. FEEDBACK ON THE COL·LABER TRAINING DAY	24
FIGURE 5. FEEDBACK ON THE COL·LABER TRAINING DAY	24
FIGURE 6. TRAINING ANNOUNCEMENT POSTER	25
FIGURE 7. TRAINING ANNOUNCEMENT POSTER	26

SYMBOLS, ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

CRM	Customer Relationship Management
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
INTEGER	Interconnecting 4 Helix Innovation Ecosystems in European Regions
T	Task
WP	Work-Package

1.INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background and aim

The aim of this deliverable is to detail the efforts and outcomes of Task 3.3, which focuses on piloting the incubation and acceleration of selected social-digital projects via regional Col-laborathons. These events served as platforms for identifying innovative solutions and ensuring their alignment with regional needs and realities. Key stakeholders played a central role in the selection process, evaluating proposals and pitches presented during the Col-laborathons to choose the most promising projects.

These activities achieved significant milestones in stakeholder engagement by establishing contact with numerous stakeholders in each region, creating a solid foundation for collaboration and knowledge exchange. Organising meetings between social-driven innovators and business leaders facilitated fruitful exchanges of ideas, potentially leading to innovative partnerships and solutions. In Catalonia, a comprehensive needs assessment was conducted, distinguishing between business-driven and social-driven approaches to innovation. This provided valuable insights for project selection and development. Additionally, strategies to promote convergence between these two approaches were identified, laying the groundwork for sustainable social projects with a broader impact.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The report describes the three mentoring processes that have been developed within the project by the teams from Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia. These three processes were carried out with the aim of providing social innovators with the tools to advance their projects towards a solid business model. Since the mentoring processes are still ongoing in the case of Catalonia, this report explains the progress made so far.

1.3 Methods

This section outlines the methods and processes implemented to support social innovators in advancing their projects towards a solid business model. The teams from Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia coordinated these efforts.

In advancing the goals of the project, several key initiatives were undertaken to foster collaboration, innovation, and sustainable impact.

- **Stakeholder Outreach:** Organizing outreach meetings with stakeholders in each region, including entrepreneurs, community representatives, and industry leaders, to foster collaboration and gather diverse perspectives.
- **Idea Exchange Sessions:** Facilitating sessions where social entrepreneurs and business leaders can share insights and identify specific needs, potentially leading to innovative solutions and potential partnerships.
- **Impactful Events:** Hosting events aimed at achieving real and sustainable social impact in projects, while also fostering income generation and collaboration with businesses and investors to identify potential long-term viability for their actions and services.
- **Convergence Strategies Development:** Continuing to identify and develop strategies that promote convergence between business-driven and social-driven approaches, with a focus on driving sustainable social projects with tangible outcomes.

- Business Support Services: Developing resources such as templates, manuals, and other materials to support social entrepreneurs in navigating business challenges and maximising their impact.
- Materials and Guidelines to Track Projects: Task leaders are responsible for providing comprehensive materials to partners, including mentors participating in supporting actions towards the project leaders. These essential resources will be made readily available on the [INTEGER platform](#), fostering seamless communication and collaboration among team members.
- Mentoring: Mentors within the Task 3.3 framework play a crucial role in supporting innovators and entrepreneurs throughout their journey. They provide tailor-made mentoring, expertise, and training that are customised to the specific innovation stage of each individual. These mentors serve as connectors, enabling each project leader to identify challenges, promote connections within the ecosystem, and support the search for regional and trans-regional solutions, either through finding services or providing the necessary training and knowledge to overcome identified gaps.

To effectively support and advance the goals of the project, a comprehensive mentoring approach has been implemented, focusing on several key areas:

- Guidance and Reflection: Mentors offer guidance and promote reflection on strategic direction, providing advice on various aspects such as entrepreneurial and innovation strategy, and facilitating connections with relevant stakeholders.
- Content Contribution: Mentors contribute to the platform by providing content, templates, and expertise, enriching the resources available to all participants.
- Ongoing Communication: Mentors engage in ongoing communication with partners to understand their needs, supervise project progress, and offer solutions accordingly.
- Structured Meetings: Monthly meetings of about 40 to 60 minutes are expected between mentors and project leaders. These meetings can be guided by a template that identifies needs, challenges, and opportunities. Project leaders are expected to fill in this template in advance and provide it to the mentors to structure the meeting. During the meeting, the next steps are identified, with an expected follow-up date and feedback from the mentor if needed.
- Regular Training Sessions: Monthly or biweekly (depending on the availability of the mentors and projects) meetings and training sessions ensure that mentors stay updated and equipped to address the evolving needs of the participants.

By documenting processes and fostering a diversity of options, mentors contribute to the robustness and effectiveness of the INTEGER ecosystem.

1.4 Synergies with other tasks and deliverables

The upcoming deliverable will provide a comprehensive analysis of the impacts achieved through the mentoring process in all three regions. It will include:

- Project Outcomes: Detailed reports on the progress and achievements of individual projects, including the implementation of innovative solutions and the measurable benefits to target communities.
- Stakeholder Engagement: An assessment of how effectively the projects have engaged with stakeholders, including feedback from participants, trainers, and external partners.

- **Skills and Knowledge Development:** Analysis of the skills and knowledge acquired by project teams through the mentoring process, including the application of design thinking, Agile methodologies, and strategic planning tools.
- **Collaboration and Networking:** Evaluation of the synergies created between different regions and the effectiveness of interregional collaboration in fostering innovation and social impact.
- **Sustainability and Replicability:** Insights into the sustainability and replicability of the projects, ensuring that the innovations can be scaled and adapted to other regions or contexts.

By focusing on these aspects, the next deliverable will provide a clear picture of the successes and challenges encountered during the mentoring process. It will offer valuable lessons for future initiatives and demonstrate the tangible benefits of supporting social-digital projects through structured mentoring and interregional collaboration.

Integrating Deliverable D3.5 with Work Package 3 and the related deliverables D3.1 and D5.1 creates a robust framework for supporting business innovation and capacity building. The regional innovation ecosystems act as dynamic environments where businesses can access tailored support services, engage in practical training, and collaborate with diverse stakeholders. The communication and dissemination plan ensures broad awareness and engagement, driving the success and sustainability of the innovation ecosystems.

2. MENTORING PROCESS IN EACH REGION

2.1 Krakow model

Figure 1. Krakow AHathon

The mentoring programme and implementation were envisaged as part of the prize for the winning team of the Ahathon event (referred to as a Col-laborathon in the project context) organised by the INTEGER Kraków Team at the end of 2023 (29.11-01.12.2023) under the **WP3-REGIONAL INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS' AS COLLABORATORY TESTBEDS URV T3.1** Co-creation digital arenas for capacity building among innovator actors in the three regions **T3.2** Organisation and implementation of one Collaborathon in each region. The winning team, SądadeX, was offered an extensive 16-hour mentoring programme by Cluster LifeScience Krakow, a partner of the AHathon. The first meeting between the representatives of the trainers and the winning team was held in the presence of the KPT team.

2.1.1 Training topic

During the initial meeting, the training needs were established and subsequently developed throughout the mentoring process. The primary focus was on design thinking methodology, incorporating elements of Scrum and Agile methodologies. The pace of the training was adjusted according to the evolving needs of the team. The aim was to equip the SądadeX team with the necessary tools to smoothly conduct the implementation phase.

Development of the Mentoring Process:

Details on the methods used:

- Co-creation sessions
- Workshops
- Design thinking methods
- Presentations

The mentoring program was initiated as an additional incentive during the AHathon (referred to as Col-laborathon in project terminology) held in Kraków. Thanks to the collaboration with LifeScience Cluster Kraków, the INTEGER Krakow Team was able to secure additional mentoring sessions focused on design thinking methodologies. As organisers, it was anticipated that the ideas developed during the AHathon would require further facilitation, including building business models, prioritising activities, and developing additional features.

The first meeting with the winning team was organised a few weeks after the award ceremony. Their needs were gathered, and a mentoring programme was developed accordingly. Meanwhile, the Krakow team worked to provide opportunities for testing the ideas in real-world settings. Meetings were held in the Dobczyce municipality, where the SąsiadeX team being supported by the INTEGER Kraków team had also the chance to present their ideas to the Vice-Governor of the Malopolska Region responsible for senior policy.

2.1.2 Implementation phase

The winning team, under the coordination of the Krakow Technology Park (KPT) and LifeScience Krakow Cluster (LSK), conducted an analysis of data and available information in the Dobczyce municipality. The study found that the municipality was addressing the issue independently, and additional improvements were not necessary. The research was carried out with the participation of the Dobczyce municipality, while KPT provided coordination support.

Additionally, the winning team conducted interviews with several older residents of the municipality, who could be potential participants in the project, to diagnose the situation of the seniors. On KPT's initiative, a meeting was organized with the Director of the Social Policy Department of the City of Dobczyce to verify the analysis of the available data against the actual situation.

KPT was involved in verifying the monitoring process, which was the responsibility of LSK, and maintained contact with city authorities to assess the feasibility of implementing the proposed service. It is noteworthy that the INTEGER Kraków Team has supported the SąsiadeX team not only in the research phase but also with logistical aspects such as transportation between Kraków and Dobczyce.

2.1.3 Social innovators involved

The selection criteria were based on the INTEGER methodology. The winning team had to base its solution on specific criteria, including:

- Concept and Innovation
- Sustainability & Replicability
- Impact

Additionally, the following questions were considered during the evaluation:

1. **Objective and Resolution:** What is the objective and resolution of your solution? Please focus specifically on how social and business-driven innovations can join forces to achieve clear implementation and provide a viable solution.

2. **Target Audience:** Who is the target audience of your solution?

3. **Value Added:** What change will this solution bring as an added value to the well-being and healthy living ecosystem?

4. **Synergies in 4Helix:** What synergies will be implemented in the 4Helix to contribute to the solution's implementation?

5. **Sustainability & Replicability:** Is your solution sustainable and replicable?

6. **Alignment with SDG Goals:** In what way does your solution address the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)?

Furthermore, all the ideas presented were characterised by the following features:

- Response to Real Social Needs: Adequacy of the solution to the identified needs.
- Intergenerational Cooperation: Encouraging collaboration across different age groups.
- Innovation: Introducing new and creative approaches.
- Replicability: Potential to be replicated in broader populations and other regions or cities.
- Benefits in Active Healthy Ageing: Providing advantages in the domain of active and healthy ageing.

2.1.4 Mentornig based on experiences and conclusions from AHathon edition I

Preparations for AHathon

On June 5, 2024, workshops were held to create challenges and plan the mentoring process. Participants included representatives from KPT, Jagiellonian University, the SIG AHA group, and local partners. During the workshops, methodologies such as design thinking, SWOT analysis, stakeholder analysis, persona creation, and Agile methods were used. Two main challenges were identified: polypharmacy, the problem of older persons taking multiple medications simultaneously, and digital exclusion, the difficulties older citizens face in accessing information and digital services.

Organization of AHathon II 2024

For the AHathon event held on June 13-14, 2024, a total of 51 participants registered. They were divided into 8 groups. The participants came from various backgrounds, including academia, business, startups, and older persons. They worked intensively for two days on their innovative solutions.

Mentoring Process

The main focus was put on an innovative mentoring process. At the event, 14 mentors from various fields, including pharmacy, project management, pitching, technology, business, academia, and external funding, were present. Mentoring was conducted in an interdisciplinary manner, where teams requested support in specific areas, and the appropriate group of mentors consulted these needs and conducted mentoring sessions individually with the teams.

Methodologies used in the mentoring process:

- **Co-mentoring:** Mentors from different fields worked together to provide the teams with comprehensive support. This approach allowed for the exchange of ideas and experiences.
- **Design Thinking:** This process helped teams identify problems, generate ideas, and test prototypes. Participants were guided through stages of empathy, problem definition, ideation, prototyping, and testing.
- **Agile:** Participants used Agile methodology, which allowed for quick iterations and adjustments in response to feedback. This helped in the rapid development and implementation of innovative ideas.
- **SWOT Analysis:** SWOT analysis was used to assess the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats related to the proposed solutions.
- **User Feedback Loop:** Teams continuously consulted their solutions with seniors present at the AHathon, asking if the proposed solutions were useful for them. This method allowed for quick adjustments and improvements of the projects.
- **Stakeholder Analysis:** Helped teams identify key stakeholders and understand their needs and impact on the project.
- **Persona Creation:** Participants created detailed user profiles, which helped in better understanding the needs and expectations of seniors.

Benefits of the Applied Methodologies

This approach resulted in faster idea generation, risk elimination through interdisciplinary collaboration, and the presentation of prototypes at the pitch deck stage by some teams. The projects were evaluated by a jury consisting of representatives from KPT, LifeScience Krakow Cluster, business, and the Krakow City Hall. The winning team, EDISONDA, was awarded for their systemic approach to medication prescription, which included a module for clinics and hospitals, a smart pillbox service, and an app to support caregivers.

Major Project Activities and Outcomes

- 3 Regional key stakeholders were recruited to participate in the mentoring and evaluation process. These stakeholders included experts from academia, business professionals, representatives from industry firms, and representatives from the Krakow City Hall and regional authorities.
- 4 Specific evaluation criteria were established based on the INTEGER methodology. An expert evaluation template was designed to standardize the assessment process. Experts were trained in the evaluation criteria and the use of the template, ensuring consistency and objectivity in their assessments.
- 5 During the AHathon, a pitching session was organized where teams presented their projects. This session included a Q&A segment in which the jury, consisting of experts from various fields, industries, academia, and the business support sector, asked questions and provided feedback. The jury acted as both experts and stakeholders to better understand the presented solutions and assess their potential.

Figure 2. Krakow AHathon

2.1.5 Social impact achieved

Thanks to the first edition of the AHathon it was possible to underline the need for social innovations as an important factor in the regional economy. Polish partners have successfully promoted the concept of Active Healthy Ageing through various initiatives and events, such as the AHathons.

In case of KPT it has led to the opening of new sectors for the Technology Park by attracting interest and collaboration from healthcare providers, senior care organisations, and social innovation enterprises. This has resulted in increased awareness, partnerships, and the development of projects focused on improving the quality of life for older adults. We have perceived that as a great example of finding innovative ideas and solutions outside of our usual focus on ICT companies. This initiative has allowed KPT to explore and engage with new sectors, such as healthcare and social innovation, expanding our reach and impact.

In case of UJ, for example new other innovative activities took place as other projects are relevant I, like i.e. Incubator of Social Innovations project, Demo Day 4.0 (March 2024).

Building on the first edition of AHATHON's success, KPT organized the second edition of the AHathon. The second edition of the AHathon further highlighted the potential of social innovations to improve the quality of life for older adults and strengthened KPT's role in promoting these initiatives. By continuing to organize and support such events, Polish partners are able to diversify its activities, promote socially responsible innovations, and strengthen the regional innovation ecosystem.

In addition to all that we are in the process of preparing the second edition of AHathon and would like to interest more regional stakeholders but also the general public.

2.2 Hamburg model

The Social Entrepreneurship reflects INTEGER's international activities at the regional level and encourages stakeholders from the 4 helixes to engage in economic activity in the context of social innovation.

The EU Commission defines social enterprises as companies for which a social objective represents the purpose of their business activities. This objective can be to contribute to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, to develop solutions to social or environmental challenges or to drive social change.

Social enterprises often take on tasks in areas that cannot be covered by the administration and therefore fulfil an important function for the city. A 'Social Entrepreneurship Strategy' was therefore developed for the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg (FHH) under the leadership of the Ministry of Economics and Innovation to specifically promote social enterprises. More than 350 people from the social entrepreneurship community were involved in the participatory strategy process alongside representatives from various Hamburg authorities, academia, charities and civil society. The finalised strategy was adopted by the Senate in January 2023. The shared vision 'Social Enterprises - driving forces for a liveable city for all' forms the centrepiece of the strategy. The aim is to create a strong ecosystem for social entrepreneurship in Hamburg that can act as inspiration and a good role model for business, administration and civil society. The social entrepreneurial impulse to act and do business sustainably is intended to create a wave that involves the entire urban society and brings it into dialogue.

To achieve this, four strategic fields of action have been identified:

- Create structures & impart skills,
- Explain & create visibility,
- Open up funding channels,
- Establish impact partnerships.

On the one hand, they aim to strengthen the ecosystem by improving access to monetary and non-monetary resources and, on the other, to create the symbolic wave mentioned above by creating visibility and cross-sector cooperation.

The *Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship*, founded in mid-2023, was created to strengthen social entrepreneurs and future social entrepreneurs. The Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship e.V. is a cross-sector alliance that was established in 2023 by seven founding members, including the Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg and the University of Hamburg. The alliance's work is based on the social entrepreneurship strategy adopted by the Hamburg Senate with its four fields of action. As an effective link between various players in the ecosystem, the alliance is committed to making Hamburg's social enterprises and their needs visible, among other things. The alliance is supported by the Hamburg Investment and Development Bank. It helps to network, educates, encourages, provides an overview, and acts as a hub for all participants from business, administration, science, politics and civil society. In May 2024, Social Entrepreneurship City Hamburg reached an important milestone: it welcomed its first members. The first batch of members comprised 61 social enterprises and so-called partner organisations that are not social enterprises but advise them, for example.

The alliance runs a mentoring programme in which various topics are addressed, such as the creation of a business plan, legal forms and type of company, registration of start-ups, start-up financing as well as coworking/hubs and real estate. The strategy therefore offers an ideal starting point for local implementation of the project results.

An interactive stakeholder map will soon go online to visualise the diversity of players in Social Entrepreneurship City Hamburg. Filterable by topic and sector, it allows interested parties to find social enterprises and other participating organisations - whether as potential business partners, employers or other collaborations.

Four pillars of support:

- **Knowledge**

What exactly is social entrepreneurship? Is 'impact' more than just a buzzword? And who or what is an ecosystem? The Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship answers the most important questions.

- **Promotion**

Tenders, funding pots, competitions - The Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship helps social entrepreneurs to keep track of the support options available. The Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship shows where in Hamburg social enterprises can find financial support.

- **Counselling**

Anyone looking for advice or support on the topic of social entrepreneurship can contact the Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship. It is the intermediary for all social entrepreneurs, with a full address book and plenty of expertise.

Example topics are:

- Interest, suggestions and questions about cooperation
- Funding opportunities for social entrepreneurs
- Questions about the current calls for funding (currently: InnolImpact and Update HH)
- Information on who is active in the subject area with comparable programmes
- Support with exchange and networking
- Connection to the network to suitable offers for strengthening and counselling
- Referral to existing advice centres with a view to the special features of social entrepreneurs

- **Networking**

Complex social challenges cannot be solved by individual players alone. In Hamburg, there are already several contact points for networking with like-minded people.

Examples of recurring networking events are:

- ImpactLunch
- LaborX Hamburg
- ImpactCouch

- Betabreakfast
- Betahaus HafenCity Lunchtime
- Black Female Business: Digital Empowerment

2.2.1 Social innovators in Hamburg

The Social-Entrepreneurship-Ecosystem:

What is the social entrepreneurship ecosystem? The simple answer: it is everyone who is somehow connected to or involved in social entrepreneurship. And who exactly now? For a rough overview, here are three major areas:

Talents:

To address the founders of tomorrow, it is important to seek contact in schools and universities at an early stage. It is also important to stay in constant contact, for example through events and platforms, in order to ensure the continuous growth of the ecosystem.

Support:

Monetary and non-monetary support infrastructure is at the heart of the ecosystem. This support can take many forms: Counselling, qualification and financial support services for new and established founders or employees of a social enterprise, for example. Support can also take the form of the provision of office and storage space or sparring partners for business development. The city, its funding institutions, foundations, the private sector, universities and providers of incubator and accelerator programmes all participate in this system.

Market & impact:

For social entrepreneurs to develop power, they need impact-orientated markets. In other words, an ecosystem is good if social entrepreneurs have the opportunity to develop viable business models and anchor their social innovations systematically - either by finding access to the traditional market or by guaranteeing their services through long-term funding.

These three areas are not isolated from each other, but interact with each other, creating connections, interfaces and structures that strengthen each other.

Not only social enterprises can belong to the ecosystem. Organisations from many other sectors can also be part of it if they can prove that they are committed to social entrepreneurship. These include foundations, administrative, scientific and welfare organisations, private sector companies and consultancies. We refer to these sectors collectively as "partners". Social enterprises that are still in the start-up phase can also apply.

As mentioned, 61 members were welcomed by the end of May. However, these include not only social enterprises, but also partner organisations that are not social enterprises but support and advise them. This network also helps to get mentoring from people who have founded a company themselves or have had similar experiences and can therefore provide targeted help.

The founding members of the "Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship" association should also be mentioned. These include the Körber Foundation, the Social Entrepreneurship Network Germany, the Hamburg Association of Independent Welfare Organisations, the Ministry of Economics and Innovation, the Kombüse Association, the Holistic Foundation and the University of Hamburg.

2.2.2 Social impact achieved

After two years of intensive work and a participatory process involving many stakeholders, the strategy was finally finalised at the beginning of 2023.

The Alliance and its office are responsible for implementing the ideas formulated in the strategy on how to establish a culture of innovation in Hamburg that conserves resources and is geared towards the common good. It began its work in November 2023 and consists of a full-time team of five people.

First success stories:

February 2024: Kick-off for the Social Entrepreneurship City Hamburg! Almost 200 people from various sectors took part in the public kick-off event. An important item on the evening's programme: 3-minute impact pitches from various Hamburg social enterprises and other players in the ecosystem. The "Social Impact Lab", the University of Hamburg, the "Hacker School" and the "MUT Academy" took part.

February 2024: Call for funding: #UpdateHamburg 2024

The "PROFI Impuls" grant from Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank (IFB) supports smaller projects and initiatives that have a positive impact on the innovative capacity of Hamburg and its economy. There is now a new call for funding in line with the Hamburg Regional Innovation Strategy: "UpdateHamburg 2024". The aim is to support players whose initiatives contribute to making Hamburg a city worth living in for everyone.

2.3 Catalonia model

2.3.1 Social innovators involved

The mentoring process in Catalonia focuses on incubating and accelerating social-digital projects through regional events called Col-laborathons, which serve as platforms for identifying innovative solutions tailored to the needs and realities of the region. During these events, key stakeholders play a crucial role in evaluating proposals and pitches to select the most promising projects for further development.

One of the prominent projects involved in this process is FoodCLIC, led by Rosina Malagrida at LivingLab IrsiCaixa, a private foundation. The aim of FoodCLIC is to promote healthy and sustainable food practices in various neighbourhoods within the Barcelona Metropolitan Area. This initiative is supported by projects like FOSTER and Cleverfood. The project began with a pilot involving 25 organizations and received support from the European project Fit4FoodBcn and the Barcelona CaixaResearch Living Lab.

Another significant project is Memima Baby, developed by Albert Munne. This project offers a musical education application designed to enhance well-being. The app enables parents to teach their children the language of music, which in turn boosts their language skills, learning abilities, and creativity. This initiative exemplifies how digital solutions can contribute to early childhood development in an engaging and beneficial manner.

The Healthy Cities Generator, managed by Marta Rofin at Bax & Company, is an online tool designed to evaluate the health impact of urban planning. This project emerged during the urban planning process in Vic and was further developed as part of the European URBACT

Healthy Cities project. Bax & Company not only maintains and promotes the tool but also seeks additional funding to improve and apply it in various contexts. This project illustrates how digital tools can support healthier urban environments.

SeniorLab, led by Karina Simieli, is a non-profit association focused on redefining society to better accommodate longevity. SeniorLab brings together committed individuals and entities to co-create new models, processes, structures, knowledge, services, and products that address the challenges of an ageing society. The association is supported by professionals and is considering establishing a foundation to further its mission.

These projects are integral to the mentoring process in Catalonia, each addressing unique social and digital needs. By leveraging the expertise of key stakeholders and the innovative solutions identified during the Col-laborathons, these projects contribute significantly to the region's sustainable development and social well-being.

2.3.2 Methodologies used

In Catalonia, the mentoring sessions are conducted every two weeks online, providing a consistent and accessible platform for project development and expert guidance. These sessions bring together experienced professionals who offer their expertise to support the growth and success of various social-digital projects.

During these bimonthly online mentoring sessions, participants present their progress and challenges, receiving tailored advice and feedback from the experts. This format ensures that the projects are continually evolving and adapting to meet their goals. The experts involved come from diverse backgrounds and bring a wealth of knowledge in areas such as business development, innovation, strategic planning, financial management, and leadership.

The process is highly interactive, allowing for real-time discussions and collaborative problem-solving. Participants benefit from the collective wisdom of the group, gaining insights that they might not have considered independently. This collaborative approach helps in refining their business models, strategic plans, and implementation tactics.

The projects involved in these mentoring sessions cover a wide range of social-digital initiatives, each with unique goals and challenges. By participating in these sessions, project leaders can ensure they are aligned with best practices and can adapt to changing circumstances effectively. The bimonthly frequency of the sessions ensures that there is regular check-in and accountability, which is crucial for maintaining momentum and achieving long-term success.

Overall, the monthly online mentoring sessions in Catalonia provide a structured, supportive, and dynamic environment for social-digital projects to thrive, leveraging the expertise of seasoned professionals to drive innovation and growth.

The mentoring process in Catalonia is structured around various well-established methodologies and tools that have proven effective in structuring and accelerating the growth of business projects. These methodologies provide a comprehensive framework for developing social-digital initiatives, ensuring they are well-aligned with strategic goals and market needs.

At the core of the mentoring process is the Business Model Canvas. This tool allows participants to visualize and design their business models in a clear and structured manner. It facilitates the understanding and communication of the key elements of their projects, ensuring all stakeholders have a coherent view of the project's structure and objectives.

Strategic analysis tools such as DAFO (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) and CAME (Correct, Adapt, Maintain, and Explore) are also integral to the process. These tools help participants identify the internal and external factors that could impact their projects. By understanding these factors, participants can develop actionable plans with defined steps and timelines, ensuring they can address challenges and leverage opportunities effectively.

Benchmarking is another crucial methodology used in the mentoring process. It involves a comparative analysis with competitors and industry leaders, helping participants identify best practices and areas for improvement. This ensures that the projects can stay competitive and continuously evolve by adopting proven strategies and innovations from their sector.

Innovation resources are leveraged to foster creativity and disruptive thinking. By incorporating new ideas and technologies, participants are encouraged to think outside the box and develop unique solutions to problems. This approach not only promotes innovation but also enhances the value generation capabilities of the projects.

Understanding and reviewing the target customer is essential for the commercial success of any project. This methodology ensures that the projects are oriented towards meeting market needs and expectations. By accurately identifying and addressing their target customers, participants can enhance their market relevance and effectiveness.

Defining a clear value proposition is also a key component of the mentoring process. This helps participants articulate the benefits their projects offer to customers, distinguishing them from competitors and attracting new collaborators and talent. A compelling value proposition is crucial for building a strong market presence and driving growth.

Financial management is addressed through the Basic Structure of Investments and Expenses. This ensures participants have a solid and transparent financial management system, which is fundamental for the sustainability and growth of their projects. Additionally, the Balanced Scorecard provides a holistic view of project performance, integrating financial and non-financial indicators for effective strategic management.

Coaching and leadership development with a systemic vision are also part of the mentoring process. These methodologies help in the personal and professional development of entrepreneurs, improving their leadership and management skills. Effective leadership is crucial for inspiring and motivating teams, making strategic decisions, fostering innovation, managing change, and developing talent within the organisation.

Effective leadership is necessary for guiding teams and projects with strategic vision and efficacy. The process emphasises the importance of inspiring and motivating teams, making strategic decisions, fostering an innovative environment, managing change proactively, and developing internal talent.

Additionally, the mentoring process focuses on mindset and mental resilience. A growth mindset promotes continuous learning and improvement, which are essential for innovation and development. Confidence and autonomy are encouraged to enhance decision-making and proactive behaviours. Adaptability is also emphasised to help participants navigate changes and new circumstances in a dynamic business environment.

Furthermore, Agile methodologies and basic automation software are incorporated where appropriate. Agile promotes iterative and flexible project management, allowing for rapid

adaptation to changes and continuous improvement of products or services. Automation tools such as CRM (Customer Relationship Management) and ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) systems help streamline repetitive processes, improve accuracy, and free up time for strategic activities.

By employing these methodologies, the mentoring process in Catalonia aims to provide comprehensive support to social-digital projects, ensuring they are well-equipped to grow and succeed in a competitive and ever-evolving market landscape.

3. TRAINING ACTIVITIES JOINING THE THREE MODELS

3.1 The Col·labor Training Day

The first INTEGER training activity that brought together all three regional models was the “**Col·labor Training Day**”, which took place on 14th of April 2024 from 9:00 to 13:00 CET.

A recording of the whole online event can be found on YouTube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G8UTIUC-2jg&t=4s> .

The session was held to transfer basic knowledge needed to become a *Col·labor*: A social innovator with digital skills who can network and boost collaborations within and across regional ecosystems, perform matchmaking activities and bring together social, business and technology-driven players. In the four hour online training, participants got to know about fundamentals and the skills crucial for this task. The topics presented were based on the exciting findings from the practical work carried out in three European pilot ecosystems: Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow. To ensure an engaging online session, interactive online elements were used through applications such as Mural or Mentimeter.

Following the overall mentoring goal of fostering collaboration between different quadruple helix actors and fostering social innovation potential, a wide range of topics had been discussed, including Social Innovation, Design Thinking, Social Alliances & Professional Networks, Project Management, Strategic Planning with the SOAR model, European ESG Criteria, Funding & Investment Strategies or Social Return on Investment. Several INTEGER partners supported the process in covering topics in the training. As external experts, Antonius Schröder from the European School of Social Innovation (ESSI) and Laia Pascual from Ship2B provided exciting

insights. A detailed overview of the events agenda, the topics presented and the supporting partners can be seen in the picture below:

INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND			
09:00 - 10:00	Welcome	Javier (moderator)	AFEdemy
	Presentation of the INTEGER Project	Rafel Nualart	i2CAT
	Short presentation of the regions – outcomes per region	3 INTEGER Pilot Regions	Hamburg, Catalonia, Krakow
	Scope of the Training; What is a Col-labber?	Jonas Bernitt	AFEdemy
KNOWLEDGE FOR COL-LABBERS			
10:00 - 10:45	What is Social Innovation? What does it mean for your (Social) Business?	Antonius Schröder	European School for Social Innovation (ESSI)
	INTEGER in a Social Innovation Pathway	Lina Silveira	F6S
	Design Thinking	Jonas Bernitt	AFEdemy
10:45 - 11:00	BREAK		
SKILLS FOR COL-LABBERS - NETWORKING & REPRESENTATION			
11:00 - 11:20	Finding Ideas for Social Innovation	Jonas Bernitt	AFEdemy
	Pitching your Ideas & Conducting Public Presentations	Mar Joanpere Foraster	University of Rovira i Virgili
	Creating Networks & Social Alliances	Willeke van Staalduinen	AFEdemy
SKILLS FOR COL-LABBERS - BUSINESS & FINANCE			
11:20 - 12:00	Business Modelling	Willeke van Staalduinen	AFEdemy
	Investment Mechanisms & How to align Businesses with the ESG Criteria	Laila Pascual	Ship2B
	Strategy Planning with the SOAR Model	Mar Joanpere Foraster	University of Rovira i Virgili
SKILLS FOR COL-LABBERS - MANAGING & MONITORING			
12:00 - 12:15	Performing Project Management	Javier Ganzarain	AFEdemy
	Showing Social Return On Investment (SROI)	Jonas Bernitt	AFEdemy
SUMMARY & OUTLOOK			
12:15 - 13:00	The Col-labber Curriculum as a Summary of Skills	Jonas Bernitt	AFEdemy
	The INTEGER Model & TheGlocal.Network	Rafel Nualart	i2CAT
	Wrap-up and closing	Jonas Bernitt & Javier Ganzarain	AFEdemy

Figure 3. Agenda of Col-labber Training Day

43 participants attended the session: 18 (42%) from Catalonia, 16 (37%) from Poland, 5 (12%) from Hamburg, and 4 (9%) from other countries. Regarding the quadruple helix areas, 20 people (46%) came from academia. In addition, 8 people (19%) joined from the public sector, 6 people (14%) from the industry and three people (7%) from the civil society. Six people (14%) joined without a previous registration. The feedback of the session had been collected with Mentimeter. The results showed a high level of satisfaction among the participants and a high level of interest in the presented contents (see pictures below).

Figure 4. Feedback on the Col·labor Training Day

Figure 5. Feedback on the Col·labor Training Day

3.2 Training session 1: “How to sell with AI and LinkedIn”

In the mentoring process in Catalonia, two training sessions were proposed for all the projects and regions involved. The first of these sessions, conducted as part of Task 3.3 on Incubation and Acceleration, was held on May 9th. The aim was to provide valuable skills and insights that would benefit the development and success of the participating social-digital projects.

The initial training session was titled “[How to Sell with AI and LinkedIn](#)” and was led by Inmaculada Vázquez Labella. This online session took place from 10:00 a.m. to 11:30 a.m. It was an integral part of the interregional initiative under the INTEGER project, designed to foster collaboration and innovation across different regions and projects.

Participants in this training session had the opportunity to learn how to effectively use artificial intelligence tools to optimise their sales strategies. They were also taught how to leverage LinkedIn to generate opportunities, expand their professional networks, and adopt best

practices for digital sales in the current market. The session aimed to equip participants with the necessary skills to enhance their sales capabilities and professional growth.

The session encouraged participants to share the information with their network of contacts and projects, emphasising the collaborative nature of the initiative. By attending the training, participants gained valuable knowledge that would help them improve their sales skills and broaden their professional connections, ultimately contributing to the overall success of their projects.

41 people attended this training session. The workshop had a diverse group of attendees from different institutions, including Education (22%), Public sector (25%), Private companies (28%), Civil society (10%), Technological center (2%), Consulting (2%), Innovation (2%) and Non-Profit/Association (3%). Attendees were primarily from the regions of Krakow and Catalonia. The feedback received was very positive, with participants expressing high satisfaction with the workshop.

Figure 6. Training announcement poster

3.3 Training session 2: “Communicate, Impact and Transform: The Im-perfect Pitch”

The second training session occurred on July 2, 2024. This workshop, featuring Cristina Saenz de Pipaón as the speaker, aimed to improve participants' communication skills, particularly in delivering impactful pitches. Cristina Sáenz de Pipaón holds a Ph.D. in Molecular Magnetism and a degree in Physics, with extensive experience in research and technology transfer. She was the CEO of Orchestra Scientific, where she developed innovative CO2 separation technologies. Currently, she is a consultant, assisting universities and research centers in effective technology transfer, and mentors startups focused on sustainable technological solutions. The session, titled "**Communicate, Impact and Transform: The Im-perfect Pitch**" helped attendees structure their messages effectively to maintain audience attention and achieve the desired impact. Cristina Saenz de Pipaón shared simple yet powerful techniques for creating unforgettable pitches that resonate with audiences.

Participants were encouraged to register and join this session to enhance their communication skills and learn how to deliver compelling pitches for their projects. This initiative was part of the interregional efforts under the INTEGER project, aimed at fostering collaboration and innovation in the incubation and acceleration of social-digital projects across European regions.

16 people attended this training session. The workshop had a diverse group of attendees from

different institutions, including Education (33%), Public Sector (13%), Private companies (27%), Business support organisation (7%), Foundation in healthcare (7%), SME (7%) and Civil society (7%) Attendees were primarily from the regions of Catalonia, Hamburg, Krakow. The feedback received was very positive, with participants highlighting the organisation of events and business, suggesting the inclusion of video examples and practical exercises, requesting more similar events, and additionally expressing that the trainer was very pleasant.

Figure 7. Training announcement poster

4.SYNERGIES BETWEEN MODELS

In the first phase of the mentoring process, significant synergies were established between the three regions involved: Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia. Each region developed its unique mentoring model tailored to its local context, but there were notable collaborative elements and shared methodologies that enhanced the overall effectiveness of the initiative.

4.1Krakow Model

The mentoring program in Krakow was initiated as part of the prize for the winning team of the 1st AHathon event (2023), known in the INTEGER project as a Col-laborathon. The winning team, SĄSIADeX, received a comprehensive 16-hour mentoring program provided by Cluster LifeScience Krakow. This program began with an initial meeting to identify training needs, which were developed throughout the mentoring process. The focus was on design thinking methodology, incorporating elements of Scrum and Agile methodologies, ensuring the team was equipped with tools for the implementation phase.

The collaboration extended to the Dobczyce commune, allowing the SĄSIADeX team to test their project in a real environment with actual stakeholders. The INTEGER Kraków Team supported the team not only in research but also in logistical aspects, such as transportation between Kraków and Dobczyce, as well as presentations on the meetings with end - users and the Vice-

Governor of the Region. The mentoring process included co-creation sessions, workshops, design thinking methods, and presentations, all aimed at facilitating the project's development and implementation. As based on this success as well the similar approach was applied for 2nd AHATHON in Kraków, (June 2024).

4.1 Hamburg Model

In Hamburg, the mentoring process was framed within the broader context of social entrepreneurship. The Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship, founded in mid-2023, played a pivotal role in supporting social entrepreneurs. This alliance connected stakeholders from various sectors, providing networking, education, and support for social innovation.

The first batch of members included 61 social enterprises and partner organizations, with an interactive stakeholder map to visualize the ecosystem. The support pillars included knowledge dissemination, promotion, counseling, and networking. Regular events like ImpactLunch and Betahaus HafenCity Lunchtime facilitated interactions among social entrepreneurs, promoting collaboration and idea exchange.

The Hamburg model emphasized the importance of an impact-oriented market where social entrepreneurs could develop viable business models and systematically anchor their innovations. The Alliance also facilitated access to funding and provided extensive advisory services, helping social entrepreneurs navigate challenges and leverage opportunities effectively.

4.2 Catalonia Model

In Catalonia, the mentoring process was divided into two parts: the first consisted of a Col-laborathon, where innovative solutions aligned with local needs were identified. The second part focused on incubating and accelerating social-digital projects through bimonthly online mentoring sessions, where experienced professionals guided project development. Projects such as FoodCLIC, Memima Baby, Healthy Cities Generator, and SeniorLab were integral to this process.

The Catalan mentoring sessions were conducted bimonthly online, bringing together experienced professionals to guide project development. These sessions included presentations of progress, real-time discussions, and collaborative problem-solving. The experts provided tailored advice in business development, innovation, strategic planning, financial management, and leadership.

Catalonia also organized two interregional training sessions as part of Task 3.3. The first, titled "How to Sell with AI and LinkedIn," took place on May 9th, focusing on optimizing sales strategies using AI and LinkedIn. The second session, "4 Ingredients for Captivating Communication," was held on July 2, 2024, and aimed to improve participants' communication skills, particularly in delivering impactful pitches.

4.3 Synergies between regions

The synergies between the three regions were evident in the shared methodologies and collaborative spirit. All regions leveraged the Col-laborathon framework to identify and nurture innovative projects, adapting the process to their local contexts. The use of design thinking, Agile

methodologies, and strategic tools like the Business Model Canvas and DAFO analysis was common across regions, ensuring a consistent approach to project development.

Moreover, the emphasis on networking, knowledge sharing, and interregional training sessions facilitated cross-pollination of ideas and best practices. By focusing on social innovation and entrepreneurship, the regions collectively aimed to create sustainable and impactful solutions that addressed local and broader societal challenges.

In summary, the first phase of the mentoring process in Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia showcased a well-coordinated effort to support social-digital projects. Through tailored mentoring programs, collaborative events, and shared methodologies, the regions fostered an environment of innovation, sustainability, and impactful change. At the end phase of the process it will be a joining sessions between three regions to share experiences and knowledge achieved.

5.CONCLUSIONS

The first phase of the mentoring process in Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia highlighted the development of distinct mentoring models tailored to each region's unique context and needs. While these diverse approaches showcase the adaptability and responsiveness of each region to local requirements, they also present challenges in finding unified conclusions. However, several key lessons and synergies have emerged from this process, informing future efforts.

Each region developed its mentoring program with a specific focus and methodology. Krakow utilized a comprehensive mentoring program initiated through a Col-laborathon, focusing on design thinking, Scrum, and Agile methodologies, providing hands-on support and real-world testing environments. Hamburg integrated its mentoring within the broader framework of social entrepreneurship, supported by the Hamburg Alliance for Social Entrepreneurship, emphasizing networking, knowledge dissemination, and impact-oriented market development. Catalonia organized bimonthly online mentoring sessions, focusing on incubating and accelerating social-digital projects with guidance from experienced professionals and interregional training sessions.

Collaborative events and interregional training sessions facilitated the cross-pollination of ideas and best practices, enhancing the overall effectiveness of the mentoring programs. Thanks to the training sessions organized by Hamburg and Catalonia, which were open to all, common spaces were created where social innovators could learn and bring new tools to their work. These sessions played a vital role in fostering a collaborative learning environment.

To achieve more cohesive outcomes and maximize the impact of future deliverables, it is essential to strive for greater alignment in mentoring efforts. This could involve adopting a unified framework or set of guidelines that allows for flexibility but ensures a consistent approach to mentoring across regions. Regular exchanges of lessons learned, and best practices can help harmonize the methodologies and tools used, leading to more relevant and impactful outcomes for the INTEGER project and related initiatives. Developing a common impact assessment framework will help in drawing more comparable conclusions and measuring the overall success of the mentoring programs in a unified manner.

In summary, while the first phase of the mentoring process in Krakow, Hamburg, and Catalonia demonstrated the strengths of region-specific models, it also highlighted the need for greater alignment and collaboration. The lessons learned about stakeholder involvement and synergies created lay a strong foundation for future efforts. Moving forward, a concerted effort to unify approaches and share best practices, facilitated by open and inclusive training sessions, will be crucial in achieving impactful and relevant outcomes for the INTEGER project and the broader ecosystem of involved projects.